

TOLERANCE DEPICTED IN THE LYRICAL NOVEL 'THE KINDNESS OF ENEMIES'

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Annotation: The following article is about the novel 'The Kindness of Enemies' by Leila Aboulela and analyzes the main features of the novel. The Writer's writing style, seeing her life in the work, and also described fascinating story of the rebel of the Caucasus, Imam Samil, a 19th-century warrior who battled to defend his home against the invading Russians and united the Muslims of the region under his iconic leadership.

Key words: kindness, rebel, Caucasus, Natasha, Imam Samil, warrior, defend, against, Sudanese, Syria, Russians, united Muslims, Leadership, Leila Aboulela.

Leila Aboulela grew up in Khartoum, Sudan where she attended the Khartoum American School and Sister School. She graduated from Khartoum University in 1985 with a degree in Economics and was awarded her Masters degree in statistics from the London School of Economics. She lived for many years in Aberdeen where she wrote most of her works while looking after her family; she currently lives and lectures in Abu Dhabi.

"Leila Aboulela's *The Kindness of Enemies*...recreates the fascinating story of the rebel of the Caucasus, Imam Samil, a 19th-century warrior who battled to defend his home against the invading Russians and united the Muslims of the region under his iconic leadership. Weaving the story of his relationship with a Georgian princess he kidnapped into a more contemporary story of mistaken terrorism, we learn much about the nature of loss, the legacy of exile, and the meaning of home at a time in our world when all three are high in our minds."

It's 2010 and Natasha, a half Russian, half Sudanese professor of history, is researching the life of Imam Shamil, the 19th century Muslim leader who led the anti-Russian resistance in the Caucasian War. When shy, single Natasha discovers that her star student, Oz, is not only descended from the warrior but also possesses Shamil's priceless sword, the Imam's story comes vividly to life. As Natasha's relationship with Oz and his alluring actress mother intensifies, Natasha is forced to confront issues she had long tried to avoid—that of her Muslim heritage. When Oz is suddenly arrested at his home one morning, Natasha realizes that everything she values stands in jeopardy.

Told with Aboulela's inimitable elegance and narrated from the point of view of both Natasha and the historical characters she is researching, *The Kindness of*

Enemies is both an engrossing story of a provocative period in history and an important examination of what it is to be a Muslim in a post 9/11 world.

The story of Shamil, whose resistance to the Russians Natasha really admires, is woven into this one. The Russians kidnap Shamil's oldest son, Jameleldin, and many years later, in an effort to reclaim his son, Shamil kidnaps a Georgian princess. The themes of identity, conflict, and belonging are prevalent throughout this book, but the author doesn't so much belabor the idea as hammer it home. Natasha, who is unsure of her position in the world, Oz, a fairly stereotypically irate young guy who provocatively beheads snowmen with a scimitar, and Jameleldin are among the characters. who assimilates with his Russian captors, loses his language and beliefs, and yet is welcomed in neither country, and Princess Anna, who believes herself to be Georgian rather than Russian, are both lost to their fathers both physically and spiritually. Of course, a novel does not have to feature likeable characters for you to appreciate the book. By the end, I simply felt uninterested in what transpired. The book's most intriguing section was undoubtedly the Georgian tale starring Shamil; nonetheless, whether Jameleldin was his father's son or a Russian aristocrat or not was not really important. In an interview I listened to, Aboulela said she wanted to recover some words she believed had been misapplied recently, such as the idea of a spiritual struggle. Her feelings, nevertheless, might overtake the story. In the global society we now live in, identity is not always about nationality, and few people I know are as fixated on it as the characters in this novel are.

The fires of September 11, 2001 not only changed the course of America's destiny, but they also shed light on a long-forgotten history of confrontation between the West and specific branches of Islam. For many of us, the present had suddenly developed in a way that was dangerous. The novel "Two Years Eight Months and Twenty-Eight Nights" by Salman Rushdie, a surprisingly whimsy tale about warring genies reigniting an old conflict in the modern era, was just added to the library of literature on this enormous subject. Another unique book has just been released that portrays the anxiety of the present while looking back to a disputed history. "The Kindness of Enemies" maps the interconnectedness of the world on both personal and political levels. To some extent, that intricacy reflects. . . .

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reigniting an old conflict in the modern era, was just added to the library of literature on this enormous subject. Another unique book has just been released that portrays the anxiety of the present while looking back to a disputed history. *The Kindness of Enemies* explores the global interconnectedness on both a political and a personal level. That complexity partly reflects the many travels of the book's author, Leila Aboulela, who was born in Egypt, grew up in Sudan, went to school in England, and now resides in Scotland. Her latest book begins there, in a solitary farmhouse in the Scottish countryside, but the unfolding narrative will transport us around the globe and back in time.

Natasha Wilson, nee Hussein, the narrator, is an aspirational young academic who has come to see an actress of Iraqi descent. Malak Raja, who is content to play Bombay aunts and Persian supporting roles, is "perhaps the female counterpart of Yul Brynner or Ben Kingsley," but she is much less successful. Natasha has been to Malak's remote home to inspect an Ottoman sword that has been in the family for many years. At this juncture, "*The Kindness of Enemies*" breaks through the illusion it is weaving to examine a mostly unremembered historical event. According to the plot, this weapon formerly belonged to the real-life Muslim leader Imam Shamil, who fought the Russians in the Caucasian War, a conflict that raged for years in the middle of the 19th century. Natasha notices that Allah is written in gold on the blade. "I placed my thumb on the crossbar; Imam Shamil's hand had previously grasped this,"

However, this book is more than just a list of timely discussion points. Natasha is confronted by a plethora of problems very immediately after leaving Malak's house: A strange harassment accusation puts her academic career in jeopardy; a terrorist inquiry tests her morality; and an anti-abortion intimidation campaign rocks her equilibrium. Her stepmother sues her after her apartment is broken into, her father in Sudan, who she has not spoken to in years, develops a serious illness. It is obvious that the plot is intended to stress Natasha out and make her reflect deeply about her half-Russian, half-Sudanese origins. Nevertheless, it starts to seem as if Wile E. Coyote could survive this fast series of hardships. All of these issues are difficult for the book to address or even explore, and they run the risk of overshadowing Natasha's more compelling internal conflict, which leads her to believe that "I was a failed hybrid, made up of unalloyed personalities."

I hesitate to express dissatisfaction, though, because Natasha's chaotic existence offers such an intriguing contrast to the masterfully plotted historical drama that runs throughout the book. Alternating chapters transport us back to Imam

Shamil and his war against the Russians, which began in 1839, without the use of any fabricated analogies or coincidences.

In all his pained humanity, the dashing mountain soldier rides across these pages. He is equally kind and crafty as he works to bring together disparate groupings. However, Aboulela primarily focuses on the experiences of two hostages who were captured on opposing sides of the battle in order to present this captivating story: the Russians raise Shamil's infant boy as the tsar's special guest after failed peace efforts. Princess Anna, the great-granddaughter of the last monarch of Georgia, is taken prisoner by Shamil's troops and sent to his mountain hideout as revenge.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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